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OSSERVATORIO VESUVIANO
SEZIONE DI NAPOLI

THE CSOB CASE

**A focused analysis on the unprecedented Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA)
recorded in Italy during the 13 March 2025 Campi Flegrei Earthquake**

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The Scenario

Campi Flegrei, located west of Naples, south Italy, ranks among the most complex and closely monitored calderas worldwide, hosting approximately 500,000 inhabitants in the “red zone” at heightened volcanic risk. Historically, this area has undergone repeated episodes of bradyseism—phases of rapid ground uplift and subsidence—most notably during the 1982–1984 crisis, when more than 16000 seismic events affected thousands of residents (Orsi et al., 1999) . Since 2005, Campi Flegrei has experienced renewed ground uplift, coupled with a rise in seismicity that became markedly more intense after 2018 and has culminated in multiple earthquakes of magnitude 4 or greater over the past few years. Research indicates that this evolving unrest is linked to the pressurization of subsurface structures by magmatic fluids and gases, which can ascend into shallow reservoirs and interact with the geothermal system. Such activity not only influences seismic and volcanic hazard but also drives significant ground deformation and degassing phenomena, underscoring the urgency of integrated monitoring efforts. In this scenario the earthquake occurred on 13 March 2025 at 00:25 UTC (01:25 local time) had a remarkable impact on both the geophysical and engineering communities, due to the significant energy released and the extraordinary ground-motion parameters recorded in the region.

In particular, the CSOB Seismic Station, operated by INGV–Osservatorio Vesuviano, *recorded a peak ground acceleration (PGA) of 114%g, an unprecedented value in Italy according to the existing seismic catalogs*. Such a record underscores both the intensity of the event and the exceptional response of a single station to an extreme seismic impulse.

The Event:

Origin Time(UTC):	2025/03/13 00:25:02
Origin Time(Local):	2025/03/13 01:25:02
Depth:	2.4 km
Location Quality:	A
Md	4.6 ± 0.3

Dati di scuotimento 44246

Versione 0.2.4 - beta 1

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Campi Flegrei

Data e ora evento: 2025/03/13 00:25:02, MD: 4.6 ± 0.3

Data creazione: 2025/03/18 14:18:04

Vedi le tracce >

Attenzione! I prodotti disponibili su questa pagina sono il risultato di procedure automatiche attivate immediatamente dopo la localizzazione di un evento sismico. Questi processi potrebbero essere affetti da incertezze rilevanti e pertanto essere sottoposti a revisioni successive.

Network.Stazione	Lat (N)	Long (E)	Dist. epicentrale (km)	PGA (%g)	PGA (cm/s ²)
IV_OCF03	40.817330	14.165150		0.7	411.62
IT_BAN	PSA >	40.813800	14.165200	0.9	172.28
IV_COLB	PSA >	40.819016	14.144606	1.1	66.1
IT_POZH	PSA >	40.823900	14.143500	1.3	36.5
IV_CAAM	PSA >	40.820065	14.142049	1.3	25.9
IV_CSOB	PSA >	40.826469	14.143963	1.4	114.5
IV_CSTH	PSA >	40.829447	14.149329	1.4	47.4
IV_CFB3	PSA >	40.809000	14.144200	1.6	105.3
IT_NAFG	PSA >	40.820200	14.178600	1.8	18.3
IV_OCF04	PSA >	40.821865	14.130858	2.3	16.0
IV_CNIS	PSA >	40.798170	14.163176	2.3	15.6
IT_POZS	PSA >	40.828800	14.130000	2.6	24.3
IT_POZT	PSA >	40.820800	14.121000	3.1	8.0
IV_CPOZ	PSA >	40.821072	14.119110	3.2	5.8

CSOB
Site Info

Even though the CSOB site was not the closest to the epicenter, we measured a PGA value that was double compared to sites at lower epicentral distances.

PGA of 1.14g recorded with a full-scale accelerometer rated at 1g: How is this possible?

The automatic system at the CSOB station recorded a maximum PGA of 1.14g—an anomalous value given that the accelerometers are configured with a 1g full-scale range.

Immediate on-site inspections confirmed that the station, its sensor housing, and the entire instrumentation chain were functioning normally, even during the subsequent aftershock sequence.

To investigate this discrepancy, laboratory tests were conducted on a digitizer identical to the one installed at CSOB. Using a Tabor Electronics waveform generator, an Agilent voltage meter, a Guralp Affinity digitizer, and a Guralp Fortis accelerometer, the team first verified the DC signal accuracy.

In an AC test using a triangular waveform, the maximum differential count corresponded to approximately ± 21.36 V, aligning with manufacturer specifications. Additional experiments demonstrated that, under rapid movements, the accelerometer's output exceeded 1g, reaching saturation.

These findings suggest that the sensor's calibration mechanism allows for gain adjustments beyond the nominal full-scale setting, and a pre-event positive offset in the digitizer provided extra headroom, thereby explaining the recorded 1.14g value.

Pre-event positive offset in the digitizer

Spectral content and dominant frequencies

- Noise

Now, we examined the spectral components of the signal and its dominant frequencies in order to explain the observed anomaly. This analysis will shed light on the underlying dynamics and help identify the factors contributing to the unusual measurement.

- We performed a comparison between the accelerometer and the velocimeter (noise signal), both calibrated according to their respective response files (amplitude scale in physical units):
 - *The data are perfectly superimposed, confirming the reliability of the measurement.*
- We analyze the HVSr for a seismically quiet days in 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025 to see if any change was appreciable
 - *no significant differences were observed, indicating that the ambient noise conditions and site response remained quite-stable over this period.*

Spectral content and dominant frequencies

- Earthquake

- We compared the HVSR with the spectra of the magnitude Md 4.6 event on March 13, 2025
 - The HV amplitude (green line in figure) is consistent with the spectral amplification, which exhibits an eye shape or a deviation in the vertical amplitude spectrum (black line in figure) relative to both horizontal components (red and blue line)*
- To check that the larger amplitudes in the **8-15 Hz frequency band** are not correlated with the event's magnitude, we compared the HVSR of two events:
 - event March 13th, 2025 (red line) Md 4.6
 - event May 20th, 2024 (blue line) Md 4.4
 - Significant differences are observed when comparing the signals of earthquakes that are similar in terms of energy but come from different sectors and distances*

Geophysical survey

- Following the Md 4.6 earthquake, a data acquisition campaign was conducted to characterize the CSOB station site and assess potential local amplification effects related to the subsurface geology.

A) Location of the seismic survey. The arrow direction indicates the data acquisition direction. **B)** Photo of the INGV staff during the seismic data acquisition. **C)** Data acquisition scheme. The black triangles are the vertical 4,5 Hz geophones. The points along the profile marked with the red stars indicate the locations of the hammer seismic shots.

Geophysical survey

■ Results:

Although the maximum investigation depth is about 14 meters, the P-wave velocity values are low and comparable to those obtained by Gammaldi et al. (2018) within the Solfatara crater.

- *We interpret the low V_p values in the shallow part of their models as being due to the presence of loose or poorly consolidated volcanic material.*

The CSOB station is located at the end of the section, where the layer with higher V_p values (1300 m/s) shows a shallower depth.

P-wave velocity model

Overlap along the profile at the location of the CSOB station

Main Considerations/Results:

- At the CSOB site operated by INGV–Osservatorio Vesuviano, was recorded a peak ground acceleration (PGA) of 114%g, an unprecedented value in Italy according to an examination of existing seismic catalogs.
- The main findings of present analysis are the following:
 - A comparison between the integrated accelerometer and the velocimeter (noise signal), both calibrated according to their respective response files, confirm the reliability of the measurement.
 - The HVSR for a seismically quiet day in 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025 indicates that the ambient noise conditions and site response remained stable over this period.
 - The HVSR amplitude of Eqk waveforms is consistent with the spectral amplification, which exhibits an eye shape or a deviation in the vertical amplitude spectrum relative to both horizontal components
 - Significant differences are observed when comparing the signals of earthquakes that are similar in terms of energy but come from different sectors/directions.
 - *Low Vp* values evaluated in the shallow part of their models can be due to the presence of loose or poorly consolidated volcanic material that could have amplified waveforms amplitude
 - The geophysical survey confirms that the CSOB station is located at the end of the section, on a layer with higher Vp values (1300 m/s) and a shallow depth.

This allows to conclude that that anomalous PGA is likely due to a local site effect rather than a source effect.

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